

LLM for automating sales and marketing

ChatGPT-powered outbound marketing automation

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Constructor Institute

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presented by

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I certify that except where due acknowledgement has been given, the work presented in this thesis is that of the author alone; the work has not been submitted previously, in whole or in part, to qualify for any other academic award; and the content of the thesis is the result of work which has been carried out since the official commencement date of the approved research program.

Maksim Skoriukov
Schaffhausen, 11 June 2023

To my beloved wife, Céline

Abstract

The B2B sales process involves various stages, including lead generation, prospect qualification, and personalized outreach, all aimed at securing successful deals. While automation tools exist that can streamline these tasks, they often lack the necessary level of personalization which is required to establish meaningful connections with potential customers. This thesis investigates the effectiveness of incorporating Large Language Models, specifically ChatGPT, in enhancing the efficiency of the cold outreach process. The goal is to develop a tool that automates the extraction of insights about potential customers and generates personalized cold outreach emails.

The tool takes as input a company's website link, a description of the product or service to be sold, and a non-personalized cold email template. By leveraging information scraped from the company's website and personal details about the target person of the outreach process (scraped from publicly available LinkedIn page and hunter.io platform), the tool generates a personalized cold outreach email. The email incorporates relevant pieces of information from the scraped data to deliver a tailored and pertinent message that addresses the potential customer's needs and pain points. The task of extracting relevant information from the scraped data and constructing personalized text is delegated to the Large Language Model (ChatGPT) with the aim of enhancing the efficiency of the cold email personalization process.

During the research, the thesis author develops a tool to enhance the efficiency of B2B sales processes by automating cold outreach tasks and improving the generation of personalized emails. The findings of the study highlight the tool's ability to streamline the B2B sales process by substantially reducing the time needed to create impactful cold emails for potential customers. Additionally, the thesis provides practical recommendations for sales teams on how to effectively leverage the tool to optimize their B2B sales workflow. Furthermore, the study sheds light on the advantages and limitations of utilizing Large Language Models for personalization tasks in marketing communications.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Thesis statement and research questions

This section introduces the thesis statement and outlines the research questions that will serve as the guiding principles for our study aimed at enhancing B2B sales through the utilization of ChatGPT-powered automation techniques.

1.1.1 Thesis statement

The primary objective of this thesis is to investigate the potential of Large Language Models, such as ChatGPT, in automating the B2B sales process, with a specific focus on streamlining the efficiency of lead generation process in outbound marketing efforts. Through the utilization of ChatGPT, in conjunction with hunter.io and LinkedIn, the study aims to automate and optimize well-established outbound marketing practices, which have shown effectiveness in improving customer engagement and enabling sales teams to achieve favorable outcomes.

1.1.2 Research questions

To achieve our research objectives, the study will address the following questions:

1. What are the components and challenges of the contemporary B2B sales process? Which of these components can be effectively automated?
2. How can ChatGPT be harnessed to automate and optimize the outbound marketing process in B2B sales? What specific capabilities of ChatGPT can be leveraged to enhance the effectiveness of outbound marketing efforts?
3. What are the limitations and obstacles associated with the utilization of ChatGPT in the context of outbound marketing? How can these limitations be addressed to maximize the benefits of ChatGPT in B2B sales?
4. How can the integration of hunter.io with ChatGPT enhance lead generation in the realm of B2B sales? What are the potential synergies and advantages of combining these two tools?

5. How can LinkedIn be strategically utilized in conjunction with ChatGPT for effective outbound marketing in the B2B sales domain? What are the key considerations and approaches for leveraging the power of LinkedIn in combination with ChatGPT?

Through the exploration of these research questions, the primary objective of this study is to provide valuable insights into the utilization of ChatGPT in conjunction with renowned tools such as hunter.io and LinkedIn to revolutionize the B2B sales process. The findings generated from this research will contribute significantly to the existing literature on B2B sales automation and offer practical recommendations to sales teams on optimizing their outbound marketing strategies. By incorporating these recommendations, sales teams can enhance their lead generation capabilities and achieve greater operational efficiency in the pursuit of their sales objectives.

1.2 Background information on the B2B sales process and the challenges faced by sales teams in generating leads and closing deals

This section aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the B2B sales process, offering an in-depth analysis of the challenges faced by sales teams when it comes to lead generation and successful deal closure. By delving into the intricacies of the B2B sales landscape, this section sets the foundation for understanding the complexities inherent in the sales process and highlights the specific hurdles that sales teams must overcome to achieve their objectives. Through an exploration of the challenges faced in lead generation and deal closure, this section seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the context in which sales teams operate and the factors that influence their effectiveness in the B2B sales domain.

1.2.1 B2B sales process overview

The B2B sales process involves businesses selling to other businesses through stages like prospecting, lead generation, qualification, presentation, negotiation, closing, and, as Lena Hohenschwert emphasizes[21], creation of value for the customers. Sales teams employ strategies to attract and convert potential customers, aiming to build profitable relationships and drive business growth.

1.2.2 Challenges in lead generation and deal closure

One of the key challenges faced by sales teams is effectively attracting new customers. Traditional outbound marketing approaches, such as cold calling, have been commonly used to reach out to potential clients. However, selling via cold emails or contacts can be particularly challenging. Several factors contribute to the difficulty of this approach:

1. Limited Response Rates: According to Julia McCoy, a VP of Marketing at "Content at Scale", cold emails often have low response rates[30]. Many recipients may perceive them as unsolicited and may be hesitant to engage.

2. **Trust and Credibility:** According to Kerry Leech, building trust and establishing credibility through cold outbound can be a significant obstacle[27]. Prospects may be skeptical of unfamiliar companies or skeptical of claims made in unsolicited emails.
3. **Relevance and Personalization:** according to Aham-adi, customizing and personalizing cold emails to resonate with each recipient is essential[12]. Yet, it is also time-consuming and requires extensive research on each potential recipient. Failing to tailor the message can result in low engagement and missed opportunities.
4. **Compliance and Legal Considerations:** Compliance with anti-spam laws and data protection regulations is crucial in outbound marketing. Sales teams need to ensure they adhere to applicable laws and obtain necessary permissions before initiating contact when applicable. Antoine Fink from hunter.io[19] gives an overview of GDPR compliance guidelines, Riya Uppal[38] gives a wider outlook on B2B data compliance in cold outreach, and Yasin Küçükaya[26] highlights main differences between GDPR and FADP (Swiss alternative of GDPR). Marc Brodherson, Adam Broitman, Jason Cherok, and Kelsey Robinson suggest companies to approach data privacy compliance with a customer-centric approach[28].

1.2.3 Best practices in cold sales

To address the challenges of cold sales and optimize the sales process, sales teams have developed efficient best practices that yield significant results with minimal effort. These best practices include:

1. **Targeted Prospect Research:** Conducting thorough research on target prospects before reaching out enables sales teams to understand their needs, pain points, and preferences. According to Anand Shah[31], this knowledge allows for more tailored and relevant communication.
2. **Personalization:** Personalizing cold emails and contacts based on the prospect's industry, role, specific pain points, plans or strategies can significantly increase engagement and response rates. According to Anan Shah[31], demonstrating a genuine interest in the prospect's business enhances the chances of building a meaningful connection.
3. **Compelling Value Proposition:** Crafting a compelling value proposition that clearly communicates the benefits and value the product or service can bring to the prospect's business is essential. According to Aham-adi[12], focusing on the specific outcomes and solutions the offering provides can captivate the prospect's attention.
4. **Clear Call-to-Action:** Including a clear and concise call-to-action in cold emails guides the prospect on the next steps to take. Whether it is scheduling a call, requesting a demo, or exploring further resources, according to Aham-adi[12], a well-defined call-to-action encourages prospects to engage further.
5. **Follow-up and Persistence:** according to the content team of Goodman Lantern[34], following up with prospects who have shown initial interest or engagement is vital: persistence in maintaining contact and nurturing the relationship can help overcome objections and eventually lead to successful deal closure.

By implementing these best practices, sales teams can significantly improve the effectiveness of their cold sales efforts, achieving more favorable outcomes and maximizing their return on investment.

Chapter 2

Literature review

2.1 Review of existing literature on ChatGPT and its impact on business in general and on digital marketing specifically

According to A. Shaji George and A.s Hovan George [11], the use of ChatGPT in digital marketing has the potential to revolutionize the industry. By using natural language processing and machine learning algorithms, businesses can automate parts of customer service and sales, while still providing customers with a personalized experience. ChatGPT can also be used in combination with other technologies like AI and analytics tools, making digital marketing campaigns more effective. The benefits of using ChatGPT in digital marketing are numerous, including increased efficiency through automation, improved customer engagement, more accurate data collection, cost savings from reduced labor expenses associated with manual tasks, and greater scalability. The technology can also provide valuable insights to businesses that they may not have been able to obtain otherwise, ultimately leading to increased ROI.

The article "The Prospects and Challenges of ChatGPT on Marketing Research and Practices" by Varsha Jain, Himanshu Rai, Parvathy, Emmanuel Mogaji[39] discusses the potential of ChatGPT AI in various aspects of marketing, advertising, and sales. ChatGPT can help marketers in content generation, customer service, language translation, text summarization, and global business. ChatGPT can also assist in various segments of marketing research such as research and segmentation, consumer behavior, advertising, and branding. However, the article also highlights the challenges of using ChatGPT in marketing research, such as data privacy, security, and ethical considerations. The article also explains how ChatGPT can assist in sales by predicting future sales revenue, micro-segmenting customers, gathering data and insights on a particular market or industry, and setting sales targets. Overall, the article suggests that ChatGPT has excellent potential in revolutionizing the marketing and sales industries but requires careful consideration of its potential risks and ethical implications.

2.2 Review of existing literature on B2B sales, lead generation, and automation techniques

Any sales process starts from defining the product to be sold and the target audience of this product.

Ray Collis and John O’Gorman in "Quick win B2B sales"[15] answer top 100 B2B sales questions. Among other things, in scope of so-called "new approach" to marketing and sales, they emphasize the importance of segmenting customers based on distinctive traits, building customer profiles and tailoring the offering to every specific customer segment, and even to every specific customer, when possible. To define an ideal customer profile, they recommend answering a series of who/what/where/when/why/how questions:

1. WHO?
 - (a) Who are they?
 - (b) Who (among our customers) are they like?
 - (c) Who are they buying from now?
 - (d) Who can introduce us?
 - (e) Who are they influenced by?
2. WHAT?
 - (a) What size?
 - (b) What sector, subsector, or niche?
 - (c) What is its ownership, or organization structure?
 - (d) What do we want to sell?
 - (e) What solutions are they presently using?
 - (f) What solution do they need?
 - (g) What priorities do they have?
 - (h) What success have we had?
 - (i) What references / examples are relevant?
3. WHERE?
 - (a) Where are they located?
 - (b) Where are they listed, advertising, attending, etc?
4. WHEN?
 - (a) When is the need at its most (triggers, critical events, etc.)?
 - (b) When is the best time to approach them?
5. WHY?
 - (a) Why do they need our solutions?
 - (b) What problems, or opportunities do they have?

2.2 Review of existing literature on B2B sales, lead generation, and automation techniques

6. HOW?

- (a) How sophisticated are they?
- (b) How long are they in business?
- (c) How much can they spend?
- (d) How much competition is there for their business?
- (e) How have we got an edge?

When it comes to doing a research on the potential customer, Ray Collis & John O’Gorman suggest the following sources:

1. The company’s own website
2. A Google search for other online references to the company (it may be useful to set up a Google alert on the company name)
3. Your company’s own sales database
4. Colleagues, friends and contacts
5. The prospect’s annual report and company accounts, if relevant
6. Trade and professional associations

They highly recommend obtaining the following information before talking to potential customers:

1. What size are they? How long are they in business?
2. What products / services do they offer? What is their core technology?
3. What are their markets and who are their customers?
4. Do they compete on price? Quality? Service? Delivery?
5. What are the key opportunities and challenges facing the company and its industry?
6. How are they performing at the moment? What is their financial situation?
7. What is their organizational structure and who are the key people in the company?
8. Who is likely to be involved in the purchase decision and what are they like?
9. What recent events (product launches, recent appointments, etc.) have taken place in the company?
10. Who do they presently buy from? What are their procedures with respect to suppliers? What are they like to deal with? Do they pay on time?
11. What past work has your company done that is specifically relevant to this company?

When it comes to personalization of outbound marketing, huge companies like MailChimp[35], who focus on providing mass email marketing services, claim that personalized emails significantly improve the open rates of emails. They suggest personalizing subject lines with the recipient’s name or location, and emphasize that personalization of emails may work especially well when combined with marketing automation in transactional emails, such as birthday deals, post-purchase follow-ups or promotional emails.

2.3 Gaps in the literature and potential research opportunities

While the use of Large Language Models (LLMs), according to Sam Crowder[18], has been gaining more and more attention, there are still several gaps in the existing literature that present opportunities for further research and exploration. In this section, we will discuss these gaps and outline potential research opportunities for scholars and practitioners in the field.

2.3.1 Limited focus on ethical considerations

One notable gap in the literature is the limited focus on ethical considerations related to LLM-powered (e.g. ChatGPT) outbound marketing. As LLM (and other AI-based) technologies become more prevalent in sales processes, it becomes crucial to address ethical concerns surrounding privacy, data security, and the responsible use of LLM in reaching out to potential customers. Future research could delve deeper into these ethical dimensions, exploring frameworks and guidelines to ensure the ethical deployment of LLM in B2B outbound marketing.

2.3.2 Integration of human touch

While LLM offers automation and efficiency benefits, there is a need to strike a balance between automation and the integration of human touch in B2B outbound marketing. The literature lacks extensive exploration of how AI technologies can be effectively combined with human interactions to create personalized and engaging outreach experiences while considering limitations of the LLM-based tools. Further research could focus on understanding the optimal blend of AI automation and human touchpoints, examining how the two can complement each other to maximize results.

2.3.3 Contextual adaptation

Another research opportunity lies in exploring how AI-powered outbound marketing can adapt to different contexts and industries. The existing literature often lacks industry-specific studies that examine the effectiveness of LLM-technologies in diverse B2B sectors. Future research can investigate the contextual factors that influence the success of LLM-powered outbound marketing strategies, such as the unique characteristics of industries, customer preferences, and cultural nuances. Understanding these factors can lead to more tailored and effective LLM-based solutions for specific B2B sectors.

2.3.4 Long-term relationship building

While LLM can support initial outreach efforts, there is a need to explore how it can contribute to long-term relationship building with B2B customers. The literature often gives very high-level overviews of the impact LLM has on the sales processes, and this specific study is focusing on the early stages of the sales process only (customer research and initial stages of contact). However, maintaining and nurturing customer relationships over time is equally important. Future research can investigate how LLM technologies can be utilized to foster long-term customer engagement, loyalty, and repeat business in the B2B context.

2.3.5 Evaluation of LLM impact

Lastly, there is a need for more empirical studies that evaluate the actual impact of LLM-powered outbound marketing on sales performance and business outcomes. While the potential benefits of LLM seem to be almost obvious, empirical evidence is crucial to validate its effectiveness, identify best practices, and guide decision-making. Future research can employ quantitative and qualitative methodologies to measure the impact of LLM on key performance indicators, such as lead conversion rates, customer satisfaction, and revenue growth.

Overall, the existing literature on LLM in B2B outbound marketing presents several gaps and opportunities for further research. Addressing ethical considerations, exploring the integration of human touch, understanding contextual adaptation, investigating long-term relationship building, and evaluating the impact of LLM are areas that hold promise for advancing knowledge and informing best practices in the field. By addressing these gaps, researchers and practitioners can unlock the full potential of LLM in B2B sales and marketing, and drive more successful outcomes.

2.4 Benefits and limitations of existing B2B sales automation tools and techniques

2.4.1 Salesforce

Salesforce, Inc. is a San Francisco-based American company that specializes in cloud-based software solutions. Their offerings encompass a wide range of applications and software, primarily centered around customer relationship management, sales, customer service, marketing automation, e-commerce, analytics, and application development.

Being a leader in the sales automation software industry, Salesforce is quite successful in keeping up with the trend of integrating LLM-based solutions into their products. According to the company's official blog[8], they recently released EinsteinGPT - a generative, AI-based (including LLM-powered solutions) tool that streamlines different aspects of the sales process.

According to StreetDigital, a Certified Salesforce Partner, the application of Salesforce Einstein GPT can vary depending on its usage, offering a range of practical applications in real-world scenarios[36]. One notable CRM feature it provides is the ability for customer service departments to swiftly identify trends in customer conversations and automate responses accordingly. Sales teams can leverage this technology to automatically classify leads, monitor customer interactions, and extract valuable insights about customer preferences. Likewise, marketing teams can utilize it to identify topics that resonate with their target audience, enabling them to tailor campaigns accordingly. By utilizing Salesforce Einstein GPT, organizations can optimize their marketing endeavors and maximize their return on investment (ROI).

According to Phil Wainewright and StreetDigital, while Salesforce Einstein GPT is valuable, it does have certain limitations[36][40]. Firstly, its accuracy falls short compared to human-led analysis, and it still necessitates manual input for generating insights. Additionally, its AI capabilities are limited to comprehending structured data sources, making it unable to analyze

unstructured sources such as audio recordings or videos. Lastly, the effectiveness of this technology relies on the quality of the data inputs, emphasizing the importance of accurate data collection and organization by the company who's using it.

2.4.2 SendPulse

SendPulse offers significant benefits for B2B sales teams, particularly when it comes to personalization capabilities. By leveraging the platform's personalization features, B2B sales professionals can create highly customized and targeted communication for their audience. According to the official documentation of SendPulse, the ability to use personalized tags[4] allows for the insertion of recipient-specific information, making messages feel more personalized and engaging. Additionally, the dynamic content feature enables the creation of customized content blocks within emails, tailoring the message based on recipient attributes such as industry or job title. This level of personalization helps deliver more relevant information, increasing the chances of capturing the attention and interest of potential customers.

Segmentation[7], as stated in the official documentation, is another valuable feature offered by SendPulse. B2B sales teams can divide their audience into specific groups based on various criteria, allowing for precise targeting and the delivery of personalized messages to specific segments. This segmentation capability enhances the effectiveness of campaigns by delivering messages that resonate with the specific needs and interests of each segment.

According to the official documentation, SendPulse also provides behavioral triggers[10], enabling automatic sending of personalized messages based on recipient actions or engagement. This functionality allows B2B sales teams to respond in real-time to specific actions, such as clicking on a particular link, with tailored follow-up messages. These behavioral triggers ensure timely and relevant communication, increasing engagement and conversions.

Despite its numerous benefits, SendPulse does have limitations. The platform's setup can be complex, especially for users unfamiliar with email marketing or automation tools. Some technical knowledge may be required to fully leverage all the functionalities. Additionally, users may encounter a learning curve when transitioning from other email marketing or sales automation solutions.

Furthermore, while SendPulse offers powerful personalization capabilities, its integrations with other sales and CRM tools may be limited. It is crucial for B2B sales teams to ensure compatibility with existing systems to avoid disruptions in their sales processes.

As for the use of LLMs, judging from official documentation, SendPulse is quite limited in this regard at this moment: the tool allows users to automate some of the user support tasks, but it does not help with automation of outbound marketing[3].

In conclusion, SendPulse's personalization functionality offers significant advantages for B2B sales teams. The ability to personalize messages with dynamic content, personalized tags, and behavioral triggers enables highly customized communication. However, users should consider the platform's complexity during setup, the learning curve involved, and potential limitations in integrations when evaluating SendPulse as a solution for their B2B sales efforts.

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Context of the research

ETH Entrepreneur Club (referred to as ETH EC hereafter), according to the official website[2], is a student-led non-profit organization that endeavors to inspire, educate, and accelerate the next generation of entrepreneurs in Switzerland. ETH EC leads numerous initiatives, including, but not limited to: Boost, Startup Speed Dating, Fuckup Nights, InCube.

Specifically, as a member of the Launch 2023 event organizing team within the ETH EC, the author's responsibilities centered around attracting partners for the Better Future section of the event. This section of Launch focuses on sustainable development-oriented companies and aims to provide support for projects related to sustainability. Illustrative examples include enterprises involved in renewable energy production, advocates of recycling and reusing goods, and promoters of responsible consumption. According to Simmi Dhyani and Meenakshi Sharma, in 2023, the concept of corporate social responsibility has gained significant traction[25], with companies leveraging it as a means to enhance their reputation among customers and demonstrate their commitment to environmental and social well-being.

Partner acquisition process is essentially a B2B-sales process: partners of Launch 2023 are corporates, startups, NGOs and organizations of other types, who pay a participation fee to ETH Entrepreneur Club for getting an opportunity to be presented at the event and engage with the visitors of the event. Depending on the business goals of a potential partner, they can choose one of the several participation packages. Each participation package offers a different set of benefits, including, but not limited to, a subset of the following options:

1. A partner booth/stand on the exhibition floor of the event
2. An opportunity to run a workshop session on the topic of interest of the participating partner
3. An opportunity to participate in the mainstage program of the event
4. Access to the pool of talents, formed from the student-visitors of the event

The features, included to the packages, are aiming at providing the following values to partners of Launch 2023:

1. Increasing the brand exposure by talking to the visitors of the event on the exhibition floor and getting promoted via the marketing materials and other marketing activities
2. Getting access to the pool of talents, presented on the event
3. Getting a change of raising an investments during the Investor Speed Dating activity
4. Extending personal and professional network

Essentially, the partner acquisition process involves actively engaging with a wide range of potential partners within the constrained time frame of event preparation. The objective is to communicate the advantages associated with participating in the event and mutually agreeing on various aspects of their involvement, such as the participation package, workshop topic (for those selecting a package with a workshop-hosting feature), and other pertinent details.

Given the author's dedicated allocation of 8 hours per week to ETH EC-related activities, careful consideration was given to utilizing this limited time resource effectively. Acknowledging the author's relatively limited prior experience in B2B sales, the decision was made to conduct research on the topic of B2B sales. This research aimed to enhance the author's understanding of the sales role within the B2B sales environment, enabling a more comprehensive grasp of the subject matter and the effective utilization of available time.

3.2 Research methods and techniques to be used in the study, such as data collection, analysis, and interpretation

3.2.1 Approach to the research and methods used

To enhance efficiency in the partner acquisition process, the author adopted three distinct approaches to investigate the field of B2B sales:

1. Interviews: author interviewed several B2B-salesmen and marketers with hands-on experience in these subjects to get a grasp of the most efficient approaches they use when launching marketing and sales campaigns
2. Theoretical research: interviews navigated the author in his theoretical research; at this stage author read more into the topics that the interviewees introduced to him
3. Practical: based on the results of both interviews and the theoretical research, the author implemented the most promising and impactful best practices in a form of an application and used this application for streamlining the efficiency of B2B sales processes in scope of his work as Partner Relations specialist in ETH EC

3.2.2 Insights from interviews with B2B-salesmen and marketers

Having a goal of optimizing B2B-sales processes in terms of efficiency, the author, relying on Customer development methodology, as stated in "Lean Startup, Agile Methodologies and Customer Development for business model innovation: A systematic review and research agenda" by Jonathan L. York and Jeffrey E. Danes[41], formulated several questions aimed at extracting insights from the interviewees. Customer development suggests asking people open questions

that are focusing on past experiences and emotions of the interviewees, and claims that this approach leads to more insightful and fruitful conversations. The list of the questions is presented below:

1. Tell me me about your job:
 - (a) What do you do?
 - (b) What are your responsibilities in your everyday work and how do you measure success?
 - (c) How much experience do you have in the field you're currently working in?
2. Tell me more about the tasks you solve during your everyday work:
 - (a) What are the steps you perform in order to get results in the work you are doing?
 - (b) From your experience, what are the practices that give 80% of results for 20% of effort?
 - (c) What are the tasks that take most of your work time?
 - (d) What tools do you use in your everyday work?

Having prepared these questions, the author approached 4 people from B2B-sales and marketing fields, and got the following answers:

Interviewee 1 (Mikhail, co-founder of a Digital-marketing studio):

1. **Q:** What do you do?
A: Launching B2C digital marketing campaigns for my customers
2. **Q:** What are your responsibilities in your everyday work and how do you measure success?
A: Launching marketing campaigns for my customers (B2C marketing)
It depends on project specificity and stage of the project, but in general I measure success as a conversion rate (e.g. from page views to purchases etc.)
3. **Q:** How much experience do you have in the field you're currently working in?
A: We started our agency 5 years ago, and since then I am involved in different facades of business development and implementation of different project
4. **Q:** What are the steps you perform in order to get results in the work you are doing?
A: If we talk about B2C marketing, then:
 - (a) I agree on the project terms with my customer
 - (b) I research competitors of the product I am promoting to determine competitors' offers and ad/sales channels
 - (c) I research the target audience of the product I am about to promote (e.g. type of occupation, demographics, language/slang they speak and etc)
 - (d) I come up with hypotheses of what customer acquisition channels I would like to use
 - (e) I come up with different creatives (phrasing of the product or service I am selling)

- (f) I launch test ad campaigns and measure the conversions
 - (g) I repeat the testing phase several times.
 - (h) Based on the tests results, I make a decision on where to invest more time, effort and money to get the best performance for the campaign I am running
5. **Q:** From your experience, what are the practices that give 80% of results for 20% of effort?
A: Building the target audience understanding (target customer profile) & use of different triggers in ad posts; Katelyn Bourgoin, CEO of Customer Camp, and Joseph Sugarman, a recognized copywriter, marketer and seller, support[13][32] the use of triggers in marketing
6. **Q:** What are the tasks that take most of your work time?
A: Routine tasks of researching competitors and target audience
7. **Q:** What tools do you use in your everyday work?
A: Google Spreadsheet, Telegram, tgstat.com, telemetr.io, vk ads, facebook ada, tilda.cc

Interviewee 2 (Lena, co-founder of a Digital-marketing studio):

1. **Q:** What do you do?
A: Launch marketing campaigns for our business-partners and promote our agency (sell our services to other businesses; so, B2B sales)
2. **Q:** What are your responsibilities in your everyday work and how do you measure success?
A: Selling our agency's services to potential partners and promoting our customer (other businesses) on social media and different ad platforms
3. **Q:** How much experience do you have in the field you're currently working in?
A: We started our agency 5 years ago; before that I worked for a few years as a marketing manager in a big international chain of pizzerias
4. **Q:** What are the steps you perform in order to get results in the work you are doing?
A: When selling our agency's services:
- (a) Prepare portfolio of project we implemented
 - (b) Make a list of potential customers
 - (c) Come up with a personalized message for a customer (e.g. praise some of their recent achievements)
 - (d) Contact potential customers via Instagram/WhatsApp/Telegram
 - (e) Try to engage the potential customer into a conversation

When promoting other companies' services or products:

- (a) Come up with the target audience profile and study their problems
- (b) Study the competitors and their ad campaigns
- (c) Come up with creatives for the ad campaigns; if possible, apply personalization to the ads texts

- (d) Launch test campaigns and measure performance
 - (e) Invest more effort and money into the best performing campaigns
 - (f) Create more complex funnels if needed (e.g. by automating the sales funnel via messenger/email bots and newsletters)
5. **Q:** From your experience, what are the practices that give 80% of results for 20% of effort?
A: Personalized approach to customers, deep understanding of customers' needs and the jobs they might hire the product for (as demonstrated in the book "Jobs to be done. Theory to practice" from Anthony W. Ulwick[37])
6. **Q:** What are the tasks that take most of your work time?
A: When advertising my agency's services – finding potential customers and coming up with some personalization takes most of the time (e.g. 5 to 15 minutes to study the potential customer's social media, website, etc.). When launching marketing campaigns for our customers – researching the target audience and their problems.
7. **Q:** What tools do you use in your everyday work?
A: Google Spreadsheet, Telegram, WhatsApp, Instagram, Photoshop, tgstat.com, telemetr.io, vk ads, facebook ada, tilda.cc, sendpulse.com

Interviewee 3 (Beatrice, Communication Project Manager in a building development company):

1. **Q:** What do you do?
A: I communicate with external partners of the company in scope of our projects, as well as do partner acquisition activities.
2. **Q:** What are your responsibilities in your everyday work and how do you measure success?
A: In partner acquisition activities my effectiveness is measured by the amount of partners I attracted. I consider myself doing my job efficiently if conversion from first contact to call is satisfying me (absolute numbers can vary depending on the project).
3. **Q:** How much experience do you have in the field you're currently working in?
A: 2.5 years in this and similar roles in total
4. **Q:** What are the steps you perform in order to get results in the work you are doing?
A:
- (a) Research on potential partners (e.g. google or browse linkedin)
 - (b) Having the list of companies ready, I look for points of contact for them (e.g. some person who is employed in the company; sometimes it can be a PR-manager, sometimes the CEO, and etc.)
 - (c) For each point of contact on the list, I prepare a personalized message; among personalization factors that I use are (not limited to): age of the contactable person to adjust the language and tone of the message, their main language, recent publications on the page
 - (d) I send the personalized message and wait for the response
 - (e) If necessary, I send followup emails or call via the phone

5. **Q:** From your experience, what are the practices that give 80% of results for 20% of effort?
A: Personalization of messages (email, LinkedIn), giving a call to the company if got no response from them
6. **Q:** What are the tasks that take most of your work time?
A: Researching on the company and then further communication
7. **Q:** What tools do you use in your everyday work?
A: LinkedIn, mobile phone, email

Interviewee 4 (Alexey, Salesman in an IT company):

1. **Q:** What do you do?
A: I sell a service of creating a website to other companies.
2. **Q:** What are your responsibilities in your everyday work and how do you measure success?
A: It can vary, depending on agreements with team members. One day I can be doing calls with customers, the other day I can be texting potential customers and so on.
3. **Q:** How much experience do you have in the field you're currently working in?
A: More than 20 years of overall sales experience, 2+ years of sales in IT.
4. **Q:** What are the steps you perform in order to get results in the work you are doing?
A:
Depends on the industry where the sales are done; e.g. B2B vs B2C would have completely different approaches and steps. In bigger companies/sales teams it's common to split responsibilities among the sales people and build sort of pipelines, for example:
 - (a) One person looks for contacts
 - (b) Second person communicates with the potential lead
 - (c) Third person, when the 2nd one agreed on having a call, does the actual call and talks to the potential customer
5. **Q:** From your experience, what are the practices that give 80% of results for 20% of effort?
A: Main goal of the salesperson is to attract attention and invoke some interest in the potential customer. It's important to understand that people make decisions emotionally, not rationally, so setting up a human connection with the potential customer is very important.
6. **Q:** What are the tasks that take most of your work time?
A: Lead generation (get people engaged in conversation).
7. **Q:** What tools do you use in your everyday work?
A: LinkedIn, databases of contacts, software that scrapes contacts from web resources

After conducting the interviews, the author has summarized the main points as follows:

1. Getting people's attention and making them read your message can be challenging, so salespeople and marketers often need to be creative when approaching potential customers.

2. Personalizing messages gives people a sense of familiarity and increases the chances of them actually reading the message.
3. Triggers are effective tools for grabbing people's attention and piquing their interest.

These insights highlight the importance of being innovative, personalizing messages, and using triggers to engage with customers successfully.

3.2.3 Theoretical research

Following the interviews with sales professionals and marketers, the author engaged in a comprehensive analysis of the gathered data to gain a deeper understanding of the discussed topics. The resulting insights and significant findings pertaining to the research are presented in Section 2.2 of this paper.

3.2.4 Practical approach. Classic approach to partner acquisition as a Partner relations member of ETH EC, Launch team

In the context of partner acquisition, ETH EC heavily relied on email marketing as a conventional method. The use of in-person networking was limited, as the organization found email marketing to be more efficient and scalable for reaching potential partners. However, the email marketing process involved substantial manual effort, including research and email composition.

The initial step in the email marketing process involved manual research to identify potential partner companies that aligned with the values and goals of ETH EC and the event. Subsequently, personalized emails were crafted, with careful attention given to tailoring each message to the specific company and contact person. The objective was to ensure the emails felt genuine and not like generic spam.

Each introductory email included a call-to-action, typically inviting the recipient to schedule a call for exploring collaborative opportunities, such as the company's participation as an invited partner in the event.

Following the initial email, the author would await a response to the call-to-action. In cases where no response was received after a few days, a follow-up email would be sent. While this approach proved effective in generating interest and fostering relationships, it necessitated a significant investment of time and effort.

3.2.5 Improving the practical approach with the learnings from the research

Based on the insights derived from customer interviews and an extensive review of relevant literature, the author has developed a comprehensive breakdown of the initial outbound marketing stage for the duties performed within ETH EC. This breakdown encompasses the key activities and strategies employed to attract potential partners:

1. Define the product; low potential for automation
2. Define potential customers (segments and profiles); high potential for automation (with the use of AI and search engines)

3. Find potential customers (company[website, linkedin page] + contact person [email, name, linkedin page]); high potential for automation (with the use of AI, search engines and special databases that collect and sell information about companies)
4. Do a research on the potential customer company to gain insights about the company that can be used for personalization of the email; high potential for automation
5. Research on the company's contact person; high potential for automation (with the use of AI, search engines, social media)
6. Generate personalized company email text and subject for the initial contact letter; high potential for automation (with the use of AI, social media and search engines)
7. Generate pre-meeting notes for the call with the company; high potential for automation (with the use of AI, search engines and social media)

Based on the author's empirical investigations and scholarly examination presented in the literature review and interview outcomes, it was determined that steps 2-7 of the process exhibit considerable potential for automation. Thus, utilizing AI algorithms along with relevant data from search engines and contact data aggregation services (for instance, hunter.io) has the potential to greatly improve the efficiency of these steps.

3.3 Tools and technologies used to automate the B2B sales process

3.3.1 ChatGPT

As stated on the official website[1], ChatGPT is a large language model developed by OpenAI, based on the GPT-3.5 architecture. It is a state-of-the-art natural language processing model that is capable of generating high-quality human-like text across a wide range of tasks, including language translation, question-answering, text summarization, and text completion. ChatGPT is trained on a massive dataset of over 570GB of text data, making it one of the largest and most powerful language models in existence. It uses deep learning techniques to analyze and understand the structure of language, and can generate text that is both coherent and contextually appropriate. With its advanced capabilities, ChatGPT has the potential to revolutionize the field of natural language processing, and has already been used in a variety of applications, including chatbots, automated writing, and content generation.

ChatGPT's language generation capabilities can be leveraged to automate outbound marketing in several ways:

1. Content generation: ChatGPT can generate high-quality and relevant content such as blog posts, social media posts, and email templates, which can be used in outbound marketing campaigns.
2. Personalization: ChatGPT can be trained on customer data to generate personalized outbound messages that are tailored to specific audiences, increasing the effectiveness of the outbound marketing campaign.

3. Lead generation: ChatGPT can analyze customer data and generate lists of potential leads for outbound marketing campaigns.
4. Chatbots: ChatGPT can be used to build chatbots that can engage with customers in real-time, answering their queries, and providing them with relevant information about the product or service being marketed.

Overall, the language generation capabilities of ChatGPT can significantly improve the efficiency and effectiveness of outbound marketing, by automating content creation, personalizing messages, generating leads, and building chatbots.

In scope of this thesis author used ChatGPT for two main scenarios:

1. Extraction and analysis of relevant information from the data about the contactable company and the outbound marketing target person in the company
2. Generation of personalized content for outbound marketing (emails, pre-call notes and etc.) based on the input, collected about the company and the outbound marketing target person in the company

While ChatGPT has the potential to automate parts of outbound marketing, it also has several limitations that must be considered. Some of these limitations include:

1. Limited data input: ChatGPT's ability to generate responses is limited by the quality and quantity of the data it is trained on. If the data input is incomplete or biased, it can negatively impact the quality of the generated responses.
2. Lack of context awareness: ChatGPT is not able to fully understand the context in which it is being used, which can lead to irrelevant or inappropriate responses. For example, it may not be able to understand the specific needs of a target audience, leading to generic and ineffective outreach messages.
3. Inability to handle complex tasks: While ChatGPT can generate responses, it may not be able to handle complex tasks such as lead qualification or response tracking. These tasks require a higher level of human intervention and expertise.
4. Dependence on training data: ChatGPT's ability to generate responses is dependent on the quality and relevance of the training data. It may not be able to generate effective outreach messages for niche industries or specific target audiences due to a lack of relevant training data.
5. Limited language support: ChatGPT's current language capabilities are limited to a few major languages, which may not be sufficient for global outreach campaigns or targeting non-English speaking audiences.

3.3.2 Hunter.io

According to the official website, hunter.io[5] is a web-based tool that helps businesses find and verify professional email addresses of individuals and organizations. With its powerful search engine, Hunter.io can quickly scan through various online sources to find the email addresses of potential customers, partners, or investors. Hunter.io also allows users to verify the email

addresses they have found to ensure their accuracy and improve the deliverability of their email outreach campaigns.

In addition to its search and verification capabilities, Hunter.io provides users with various email outreach tools, such as email campaign management, personalized email templates, and automated email sending. These features help businesses streamline their email marketing efforts and save time on manual tasks like researching email addresses and composing outreach messages.

Overall, Hunter.io is a valuable tool for businesses looking to improve their outbound marketing efforts by automating the process of finding and verifying email addresses, as well as managing and sending personalized email campaigns.

In scope of this thesis hunter.io is mainly used as a source of data about contact persons in contactable companies (email, first and last names, position in the company).

Some of the limitations of hunter.io as a data source:

1. **Limited accuracy:** While Hunter.io can help you find email addresses for specific domains, its accuracy is not always perfect. It may not always provide the correct email format or may not be able to find the email address at all. In such cases, manual research and verification may be required.
2. **Limited information:** While Hunter.io can provide you with email addresses, it may not provide you with other important information about the prospect such as job title, industry, or company size. This can limit your ability to personalize your outreach efforts and tailor your message to the prospect's specific needs.
3. **Limited search capabilities:** Hunter.io's search capabilities are limited to specific domains and may not be able to find email addresses for individuals outside of these domains. This can limit the scope of your outreach efforts.
4. **Limited automation:** While Hunter.io can help you automate the process of finding email addresses, it may not be able to automate the entire outreach process. You may still need to manually compose and send emails, which can be time-consuming.
5. **Data protection regulations:** Hunter.io's database of email addresses may not always be compliant with data protection regulations, which can pose a risk for businesses that use the platform for outbound marketing. It is important to ensure that any data used for outbound marketing is obtained in a legal and ethical manner.

3.3.3 LinkedIn

According to the official website[6], LinkedIn is a social networking platform designed for professionals, where users can create profiles highlighting their work experience, education, and skills. It is a powerful tool for outbound marketing as it allows users to connect with potential customers or partners in their industry. LinkedIn provides a vast database of professionals, which can be utilized for targeted outreach campaigns.

LinkedIn also offers features that enable users to filter and sort through potential targets based on various criteria such as job title, company size, and industry. This allows outbound marketers to identify potential targets more efficiently and effectively. Additionally, LinkedIn's messaging system allows for personalized outreach to potential customers or partners, increasing the likelihood of a positive response.

In recent years, LinkedIn has also introduced its own marketing solutions, such as Sponsored Content and Sponsored InMail, which allow businesses to reach a wider audience and engage with potential customers directly through their LinkedIn feed or inbox. This provides another avenue for outbound marketing and enables businesses to leverage the power of LinkedIn's platform to connect with their target audience.

In the context of this thesis, the author leverages LinkedIn as a supplementary data source for gathering information about companies and their representatives (the targets of outbound marketing campaigns). This data supports the personalization of the outbound marketing emails.

Regarding the limitations of utilizing LinkedIn as a data source for an outbound marketing automation tool, the primary constraints are as follows:

1. Anti-scraping: LinkedIn is quite strict when it comes to regulating access to the data about users of this social network. Access to LinkedIn's API is very limited and hard to get access to (requires partnership of the company, requesting the access to the data, with LinkedIn).
2. Data protection regulations: depending on various factors, data regulations can be a serious problem when it comes to scraping the information about companies and people from LinkedIn.

Chapter 4

Design and development

This section presents the key stages involved in the development of the outbound marketing tool.

The entire development process can be divided into the following components:

1. Defining the solution steps based on the research conducted within the scope of this thesis.
2. Selecting the steps to be automated, taking into account the capabilities and limitations of ChatGPT and other relevant tools.
3. Determining the appropriate technical stack for implementing the solution.
4. Implementing the solution and conducting testing using real input data.

4.1 Outline steps of a solution based on the research that was conducted in scope of this thesis

Based on findings from section 3.2.5, the author finalized the list of the outbound marketing process steps in scope of the research as it follows below:

1. Come up with a product description (manually)
2. Decide on the segment/profile of the customer to be reached out to (manually)
3. Gather links to websites of potential customers (manually)
4. Generate non-personalized template of an email and a email subject for outbound marketing (manually; with ChatGPT assistance)
5. Extract information about the company from the company's website (automatically; ChatGPT for data extraction)
6. Find a contact person of the potential partner company to reach out to (automatically; hunter.io as data source, ChatGPT for data extraction)

7. Gather information on the personal background of the contact person of the company (automatically; hunter.io + Google + linkedIn as data sources, ChatGPT for data extraction)
8. Generate personalized emails and email subjects for partners (automatically; ChatGPT for text generation)

4.2 Benefits and limitations of LLM (ChatGPT) in the solution

The author used ChatGPT for two main scenarios:

1. Extraction of the data from poorly structured text data (scraped web page contents of LinkedIn and Google) and structured data (JSONs from hunter.io API)
2. Generation of personalized email text and subject

Below are the benefits of using ChatGPT for data extraction tasks:

1. Data extraction process is time-efficient: depending on the size of the webpage and the desired size of the output, ChatGPT yields the extracted webpage data within a timeframe of 1-5 seconds
2. Data extraction is language-agnostic: the language of the webpage does not matter for ChatGPT. According to Botpress Community[16], ChatGPT supports the following languages: English, Spanish, French, German, Portuguese, Italian, Dutch, Russian, Arabic, and Chinese.
3. Data extraction instructions implementation and maintenance can be done in a time-efficient way, with little to no software development skills required.

While ChatGPT demonstrates overall effectiveness and efficiency in data extraction tasks, it is important to acknowledge certain limitations that should be considered, particularly in the context of ChatGPT version 3.5. A significant constraint is the restricted number of input tokens allowed. For this research, ChatGPT 3.5 is utilized. According to Sahil Kapoor, it supports text inputs of up to 4096 tokens, roughly equivalent to 8000 words or four to five pages of a book[24]. While this token limit is sufficient for the purposes of this study, it may prove critical for other applications relying on ChatGPT.

In addition to data extraction, the author applies ChatGPT for text generation purposes, including the creation of a general email letter template and personalized sentences for outbound marketing email content. The utilization of ChatGPT for text generation tasks has provided the following advantages:

1. Language-agnostic text generation: ChatGPT can generate texts in any of the languages it supports - despite the input prompt language. The list of the supported languages can be found in the article authored by Botpress Community[16].
2. Text generation process is time-efficient: the author of the study experienced text generation times from 1 to 5 seconds per generation.

3. Based on Cezary Gesikowski's study[20], a high level of correctness with little to no language mistakes.

Bernard Marr gives a high-level overview of ChatGPT limitations[29]. Limitations of ChatGPT, worth consideration in the scope of this research, include (but are not limited to):

1. One notable limitation of ChatGPT, according to Sahil Kapoor, is the presence of a limited context window[24]. As the input text grows larger, the quality of the generated output by ChatGPT tends to diminish. There is a threshold beyond which the model begins to "forget" the context of previous interactions when provided with additional input. However, within the scope of this research, the impact of this limitation is negligible since the text inputs employed are relatively small in size. David Coldewey reviews ChatGPT of version 4 which addresses this limitation, as well as some other limitations[14].
2. According to kangalow[23], an important aspect to consider when working with ChatGPT is its non-deterministic nature in generating outputs. Even when provided with the same input, the model often produces different outputs. This characteristic poses a challenge for tasks requiring consistent and deterministic results. In order to address this limitation within the context of this research, a decision was made to not delegate the generation of complete outbound marketing email texts to ChatGPT. Instead, the email template was fixed, and ChatGPT was utilized solely for generating a concise and personalized fragment of the email, typically consisting of a single sentence. This approach helped to mitigate the non-deterministic nature of ChatGPT outputs and maintain a more controlled and consistent output for the specific task at hand.

4.3 Step-by-step demonstration of the solution

In this section, a comprehensive demonstration of the tool's functionality is presented. The step-by-step process showcases the tool's operations, accompanied by sample inputs, outputs, and corresponding comments provided by the author. This demonstration serves to illustrate the practical implementation and effectiveness of the tool in real-world scenarios, highlighting its capabilities and outcomes.

4.3.1 Come up with a product description

The author came up with the following description of the product he was selling:

```
1 Launch - the biggest event for the entrepreneurial ecosystem of
2 Switzerland, taking place in Zürich on October 13th 2023.
3 In scope of this event there is an exhibition with a separate space,
4 called Better Future, devoted to companies who foster
5 sustainable development.
```

4.3.2 Decide on the segments/profile of the customer to be reached out

As a partner relations specialist in ETH EC, the author was focusing on attracting partners to the Better Future section of the Launch 2023 event. A typical resident of Better Future space is

a company or a startup, focusing on sustainability (for instance, renewable energy producers, eco-friendly materials researchers and others).

4.3.3 Gather links to websites of potential customers

To compile a list of potential customer websites, the author conducted a manual search process. This involved exploring the "Similar companies" section on LinkedIn, reading articles and digests featuring sustainability-focused startups, and using search engines with relevant keywords like "sustainability" and "renewable energy". These efforts resulted in a curated collection of website links belonging to companies that met the desired criteria, providing a foundation for further analysis and application in the research project.

The result of the links collection step was an XLS-file with a list of https-links to websites of potential partners.

For the purpose of this demo, the author suggested taking a link to one of such potential partners' website:

```
1 https://www.smartbreed.ch
```

4.3.4 Generate non-personalized template of an email and a email subject for outbound marketing

The author generated the following non-personalized template of an email:

```
1 {greeting} {contactFirstName},
2
3 I'm Max, and I'm organizing this year's biggest event for the
4 entrepreneurial ecosystem of Switzerland in Zürich (by
5 ETH Entrepreneur Club) - Launch. {personalizedSentence}
6 At ETH EC, we're fully committed to promoting sustainability
7 and would like to explore partnership opportunities
8 with {companyName} in this area.
9
10 Please let me know if you're available for a call
11 to discuss a potential partnership.
12
13 Best regards,
14 Max
```

And the following email subject template:

```
1 {companyName} and ETH EC - partnership?
```

Below is a list of variables that shall be replaced with the values that are relevant to a specific person and company:

Variable	Value
greeting	Either "Dear" or "Hi" – depending on what's appropriate (based on the LinkedIn page of the contactable person)
contactFirstName	First name of the contact person in the company
personalizedSentence	A personalized sentence, generated by ChatGPT with consideration of the data, relevant to the company and the product
companyName	Name of the company that is being contacted

4.3.5 Extract information about the company from the company's website

Below is the information that was automatically scrapped from the company's website (<https://www.smartbreed.ch>):

```

1 Weiter zu den Hauptinhalten
2 HOME
3 KUNDENLÖSUNG
4 FÜR UNSEREN PLANETEN
5 ÜBER UNS
6 KONTAKT
7 DE
8 EN
9 Dezentrale Upcycling-Technologie zur vollen Ausschöpfung des Potenzials
   von Insekten
10 UNSER SERVICE
11 Heuschrecken- und Grillenzucht für Zoos
12 Ansehen
13 Mehlwürmer aus Mühlennachprodukten
14 Ansehen
15 Soldatenfliegen aus organischen Abfällen
16 Ansehen
17 Supported by:
18 KONTAKT
19 Kontakt
20 Vorname
21 Nachname
22 E-Mail-Adresse eingeben
23 Betreff eingeben
24 Nachricht eingeben
25 Absenden
26 SmartBreed AG

```

It is important to note that the website information is in German language, but ChatGPT is capable of interpreting and utilizing this information for personalizing the email template,

which is in English language, without any difficulties. This enables effective cross-lingual communication and customization of the outreach emails for potential customers.

4.3.6 Find a target person for the outreach within the potential partner company

The researcher utilized the hunter.io API to identify a target person for outreach within the prospective partner organization. Below is an example of the API response for the explorable company website:

```
1 {
2   "domain": "smartbreed.ch",
3   "disposable": false,
4   "webmail": false,
5   "accept_all": false,
6   "pattern": "{first}.{last}",
7   "organization": "Smart Breed",
8   "description": null,
9   "twitter": null,
10  "facebook": null,
11  "linkedin": "https://linkedin.com/company/smartbreed",
12  "instagram": null,
13  "youtube": null,
14  "technologies": [
15    "angularjs",
16    "react",
17    "recaptcha",
18    "sentry",
19    "wix"
20  ],
21  "country": null,
22  "state": null,
23  "city": null,
24  "postal_code": null,
25  "street": null,
26  "emails": [
27    {
28      "value": "<REDACTED>@smartbreed.ch",
29      "type": "personal",
30      "confidence": 99,
31      "sources": [
32        {
33          "domain": "foodward.ch",
34          "uri": "http://foodward.ch/weiterbildungsprogramm-
          excellence-in-food/dozierende",
35          "extracted_on": "2022-05-05",
```

```
36         "last_seen_on": "2023-05-16",
37         "still_on_page": true
38     },
39     {
40         "domain": "smartbreed.ch",
41         "uri": "http://smartbreed.ch/team",
42         "extracted_on": "2022-05-20",
43         "last_seen_on": "2022-05-20",
44         "still_on_page": false
45     }
46 ],
47 "first_name": "Christoph",
48 "last_name": "<REDACTED>",
49 "position": "Managing Partner",
50 "seniority": "executive",
51 "department": "management",
52 "linkedin": "https://www.linkedin.com/in/christoph-<REDACTED>-25
53     a3286b/",
54 "twitter": null,
55 "phone_number": null,
56 "verification": {
57     "date": "2023-03-03",
58     "status": "valid"
59 }
60 },
61 {
62     "value": "<REDACTED>@smartbreed.ch",
63     "type": "personal",
64     "confidence": 98,
65     "sources": [
66         {
67             "domain": "smartbreed.ch",
68             "uri": "http://smartbreed.ch/datenschutz",
69             "extracted_on": "2022-05-20",
70             "last_seen_on": "2022-05-20",
71             "still_on_page": false
72         },
73         {
74             "domain": "smartbreed.ch",
75             "uri": "http://smartbreed.ch/team",
76             "extracted_on": "2022-05-20",
77             "last_seen_on": "2022-05-20",
78             "still_on_page": false
79         }
80     ],
81     "first_name": "Patrik",
82     "last_name": "<REDACTED>",
```

```
82     "position": "Cofounder",
83     "seniority": null,
84     "department": "executive",
85     "linkedin": "https://www.linkedin.com/in/christoph-<REDACTED>-25
      a3286b/",
86     "twitter": null,
87     "phone_number": null,
88     "verification": {
89         "date": "2023-02-22",
90         "status": "valid"
91     }
92 },
93 {
94     "value": "<REDACTED>@smartbreed.ch",
95     "type": "personal",
96     "confidence": 97,
97     "sources": [
98         {
99             "domain": "smartbreed.ch",
100            "uri": "http://smartbreed.ch/team",
101            "extracted_on": "2022-05-20",
102            "last_seen_on": "2022-05-20",
103            "still_on_page": false
104        }
105    ],
106    "first_name": "Adrian",
107    "last_name": "<REDACTED>",
108    "position": "Cofounder",
109    "seniority": null,
110    "department": "executive",
111    "linkedin": "https://www.linkedin.com/in/christoph-<REDACTED>-25
      a3286b/",
112    "twitter": null,
113    "phone_number": null,
114    "verification": {
115        "date": null,
116        "status": null
117    }
118 },
119 {
120     "value": "contact@smartbreed.ch",
121     "type": "generic",
122     "confidence": 95,
123     "sources": [
124         {
125             "domain": "swissinnovationchallenge.ch",
126             "uri": "http://swissinnovationchallenge.ch/teilnehmerinnen
```

```
127         -2020-o-z.html",
128         "extracted_on": "2022-09-01",
129         "last_seen_on": "2023-03-04",
130         "still_on_page": true
131     },
132     {
133         "domain": "swissinnovationchallenge.ch",
134         "uri": "http://swissinnovationchallenge.ch/teilnehmerinnen-2020-o-z-583472.html",
135         "extracted_on": "2022-07-24",
136         "last_seen_on": "2023-04-24",
137         "still_on_page": true
138     },
139     {
140         "domain": "sph.ethz.ch",
141         "uri": "http://sph.ethz.ch/projects/smartbreed",
142         "extracted_on": "2021-12-23",
143         "last_seen_on": "2023-05-10",
144         "still_on_page": true
145     },
146     {
147         "domain": "mindmaps.dka.global",
148         "uri": "http://mindmaps.dka.global/firms/25220",
149         "extracted_on": "2021-09-29",
150         "last_seen_on": "2023-02-14",
151         "still_on_page": true
152     },
153     {
154         "domain": "smartbreed.ch",
155         "uri": "http://smartbreed.ch/impressum",
156         "extracted_on": "2022-05-20",
157         "last_seen_on": "2022-05-20",
158         "still_on_page": false
159     },
160     {
161         "domain": "sph.ethz.ch",
162         "uri": "http://sph.ethz.ch/category/projects",
163         "extracted_on": "2020-01-02",
164         "last_seen_on": "2020-07-03",
165         "still_on_page": false
166     },
167     {
168         "domain": "smartbreed.ch",
169         "uri": "http://smartbreed.ch",
170         "extracted_on": "2019-12-31",
171         "last_seen_on": "2022-05-20",
172         "still_on_page": false
```

```
172     },
173     {
174         "domain":"sph.ethz.ch",
175         "uri":"http://sph.ethz.ch/smartbreed-gmbh",
176         "extracted_on":"2019-12-11",
177         "last_seen_on":"2021-09-23",
178         "still_on_page":false
179     }
180 ],
181 "first_name":null,
182 "last_name":null,
183 "position":null,
184 "seniority":null,
185 "department":"support",
186 "linkedin":null,
187 "twitter":null,
188 "phone_number":null,
189 "verification":{
190     "date":null,
191     "status":null
192 }
193 }
194 ],
195 "linked_domains":[]
196 }
```

The researcher employed the following ChatGPT prompt to extract from the API response the most suitable person to serve as a target person for further outreach:

```
1 I will give you a JSON with emails of people working in the company
   owning the website you have just analyzed.
2 From that list choose a person that will be the best person of contact
   for me to offer them the product that I described in my previous
   message. In response to this message send me only a JSON with the
   following fields of the contact person of your choice:
3
4 1) contactPersonFirstName - "first_name" field of the chosen person
5 2) contactPersonLastName - "last_name" field of the chosen person
6 3) contactPersonEmail - "value" field of the chosen person
7 4) contactPersonPosition - "position" field of the chosen person
8 5) contactPersonDepartment - "department" field of the chosen person
9 6) contactPersonLinkedIn - "linkedin" field of the chosen person
10
11 Generate and send me a json only.
12
13 Here is the JSON with emails, respond only with a JSON in accordance with
   the structure above and nothing else: {emails}
```

{emails} in the prompt above shall be substituted with the contents of the "emails" field of hunter.io API response above.

Upon executing this prompt in ChatGPT, the recommendation of Christoph emerged as a suitable contact person for the intended outbound marketing campaign.

4.3.7 Gather information on the personal background of the contact person of the company

hunter.io's API response contains a link to the webpage of the suggested contact person, so the link can be used for scraping information from the personal LinkedIn profile page.

Below is a deduplicated extract from the scraped content of the LinkedIn page of the contact person (full scraped content would make the document unnecessary lengthy and hard to read):

```

1 1
2 Christoph <REDACTED>
3 2nd degree connection
4 2nd
5 Co-Founder, CEO bei SmartBreed
6 SmartBreed AG Cass Business School
7 Greater Zurich Area Contact info
8 500+ connections
9 Maria Giovanna Demontis, Jim Pulcrano, and 1 other mutual connection
10 Connect
11 Message
12 Activity
13 1,679 followers
14 Christoph hasn't posted lately
15 Christophs recent posts and comments will be displayed here.
16 Show all activity
17 Experience
18 Co-Founder, CEO
19 SmartBreed AG
20 Nov 2019 - Present 3 yrs 7 mos
21 Schweiz
22 (Senior) Consultant
23 Simon-Kucher & Partners
24 2016 - 2020 4 yrs
25 Zürich und Umgebung, Schweiz
26 Internship: Equity Sales
27 Citi
28 Mar 2015 - Sep 2015 7 mos
29 Frankfurt am Main und Umgebung, Deutschland
30 Internship: Trading - Securities Lending & Financing
31 UBS Investment Bank
32 Jul 2014 - Feb 2015 8 mos

```

33 | Internship: Business Analyst GI Claims Controlling
34 | Zurich Insurance Company Ltd.
35 | Jul 2013 - Sep 2013 3 mos
36 | Education
37 | Cass Business School
38 | Master of Science (MSc), Banking and International Finance
39 | 2015 - 2016
40 | University of St.Gallen
41 | Bachelor Volkswirtschaft, Angewandte Volkswirtschaftslehre
42 | 2011 - 2014
43 | Languages
44 | English
45 | Full professional proficiency
46 | French
47 | Limited working proficiency
48 | German
49 | Native or bilingual proficiency
50 | Show all 4 languages
51 | Interests
52 | Top Voices
53 | Companies
54 | Groups
55 | Newsletters
56 | Schools
57 | Richard Branson
58 | Founder at Virgin Group
59 | 19,795,767 followers
60 | Follow
61 | Melinda French Gates
62 | Co-chair of the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation. Founder of Pivotal
 Ventures. Author of The Moment of Lift.
63 | 7,252,795 followers
64 | Show all 7 Top Voices
65 | People also viewed
66 | Hendrik Nelis
67 | 3rd
68 | Third degree connection
69 | Consultant at Boston Consulting Group (BCG)
70 | Philippe Sahli
71 | 2nd
72 | Second degree connection
73 | Co-Founder & CEO at Yokoy | Forbes 30 under 30
74 | Patrick Kessel profile picture
75 | Patrick Kessel
76 | CEO & co-founder at PeriVision
77 | Philippe Ganz
78 | CEO and Co-Founder at aiEndoscopic | Forbes 30 Under 30

```

79 Delano Fischer
80 CEO & CO-FOUNDER kaisin. AG
81 Show more
82 People you may know
83 Emmanouil Cheirakis
84 Student at ETH Zürich
85 Enora Marrec
86 Master's student in Biology
87 Boran Deniz Yaral o lu
88 Student at ETH Zurich | Master of Science in Management, Technology and
    Economics
89 En-Yu Jenp
90 Student, ETH Zurich
91 Krystsina Saiko
92 Quantitative Environmental Science @UZH | Sustainability and Food Systems
    | Yoga coaching
93 0 notifications total
94 Skip to search
95 Skip to main content
96 Close jump menu
97 new feed updates notifications
98 Home
99 My Network
100 Jobs
101 Messaging
102 1 new notification
103 Notifications
104 Me
105 For Business
106 Try Premium for free

```

Based on this scraped information, ChatGPT decides on the personalization of the greeting in the email.

4.3.8 Generate personalized emails and email subjects for partners

Based on the input data from the previous subsections, the author got the following final result: Personalized email subject:

```

1 SmartBreed AG and ETH EC - partnership?

```

Personalized email text:

```

1 Dear Christoph,
2
3 I'm Max, and I'm organizing this year's biggest event for the

```

```

4 | entrepreneurial ecosystem of Switzerland in Zürich
5 | (by ETH Entrepreneur Club) - Launch.
6 |
7 | I am impressed by SmartBreed's decentralized upcycling
8 | technology that fully exploits the potential of insects
9 | for a sustainable future. At ETH EC, we're fully committed
10 | to promoting sustainability and would like to explore
11 | partnership opportunities with SmartBreed AG in this area.
12 |
13 | Please let me know if you're available for a call
14 | to discuss a potential partnership.
15 |
16 | Best regards,
17 | Max

```

The elements of personalization and customization, generated with the use of ChatGPT, hunter.io and LinkedIn, are highlighted in bold in the texts of the email and the subject.

Below follows the prompt the author used for getting personalized sentence, personalized subject and company name for the email text and subject:

```

1 | Let's play a role-play game. Below are the rules of the game.
2 |
3 | I am Max, I am working in Partner Relations of ETH Entrepreneur Club, and
4 | I am writing cold outreach emails to sell participation in the Launch
5 | event to different companies. Description of what Launch event is: "{
6 |   productDescription}".
7 |
8 | I, Max, in my further messages will be sending you texts, scrapped from
9 | web-pages of companies I am reaching out to.
10 |
11 | You are a text scrapping and sentence generating tool that receives text
12 | input in human language and responds to each of my messages with a
13 | json-document, containing only the following text fields (no other
14 | data, but a valid json-document, containing the fields below):
15 |
16 | 1) companyName - contains name of the company, mentioned in the text that
17 | I provided you with
18 |
19 | 2) personalizedSentence - one sentence (exactly one sentence, not more)
20 | of a kind "I am impressed by .." (without mentioning Launch itself,
21 | only mentioning facts about the company I am reaching out to that a
22 | relevant for the Launch description) for a personalized offer for my
23 | cold outreach email based on description of Launch and the text that I
24 | scrapped from the webpage of the company I am reaching out to
25 |
26 | 3) personalizedSubject - a subject for the email in the format "{
27 |   emailSubjectTemplate}"
28 |
29 | . Generate and send me a json only that sentence and nothing else: {

```

```
pageText}
```

Below is a list of variables used in the prompt and meanings of these variables:

Variable	Value
productDescription	Description of the product that the author is selling via cold emails
emailSubjectTemplate	Template of the email subject
pageText	Text, scraped from the company's webpage

4.4 Choosing the technical stack for the solution

According to ChatGPT awesome list[17], ChatGPT API client libraries are available at least for the following programming languages:

Python, JavaScript, Golang, Rust, TypeScript, Kotlin, Swift, PHP, Node.js, Dart, Java, .NET, Ruby, Delphi.

For implementation of the tool the author chose TypeScript/NodeJS for the following reasons:

1. **Strongly Typed Language:** TypeScript is a statically typed superset of JavaScript that provides compile-time type checking. It helps catch potential errors and provides better code quality and reliability. By enforcing type safety, TypeScript reduces runtime errors and enhances overall code maintainability.
2. **Large Ecosystem and Community Support:** TypeScript and Node.js have a vast and active developer community, providing access to a rich ecosystem of libraries, frameworks, and tools. This ecosystem allows developers to leverage pre-existing solutions, reducing development time and effort. Additionally, the strong community support ensures regular updates, bug fixes, and improvements to both TypeScript and Node.js.
3. **Scalability and Performance:** Node.js is built on Chrome's V8 JavaScript engine, which provides high-performance execution. Its event-driven, non-blocking I/O model makes it well-suited for handling concurrent requests and building scalable applications. Additionally, TypeScript's static typing and compile-time optimizations can help improve runtime performance, especially in larger codebases.
4. **NodeJS gives access to Puppeteer,** which is a flexible browser emulation library that allows web scraping on dynamic websites (e.g. LinkedIn in our case).

The author used nodejs v18.14.0 and TypeScript v5.0.4 for implementing the tool.

4.5 Source code of the solution

Below is the source code of the tool in TypeScript:

```
1 import puppeteer from 'puppeteer';
2 import { ChatGPTAPI } from 'chatgpt';
3 import * as fs from 'fs';
4 import xlsx, { parse } from 'node-xlsx';
5 import EmailHunter from 'hunter.io';
6
7 const OPENAI_API_KEY = '<API-KEY>';
8
9 const gptAPI = new ChatGPTAPI({
10   apiKey: OPENAI_API_KEY,
11   completionParams: {
12     model: 'gpt-3.5-turbo',
13     temperature: 0.5,
14     top_p: 0.8
15   },
16 });
17
18
19 const HUNTER_IO_API_KEY = '<API-KEY>';
20 const hunter = new EmailHunter(HUNTER_IO_API_KEY);
21
22
23 function replaceAll(text: string, search: string, replace: string) {
24   return text.split(search).join(replace);
25 }
26
27 function worksheetDataToObject(data: string[][]): any {
28   const headers = data[0];
29
30   const rows = data.filter((r: string[], i: number) => r.length > 0 &&
31     i > 0);
32
33   return rows.map(row => headers.reduce((all: {}, field: string, i:
34     number) => {
35       console.log('row: ', row, field);
36
37       all[field] = row[i] || null;
38       return all;
39     }, {}));
40 }
41
42 function saveWorkseets(settings: Settings, companies: CompanyInfo[],
43   debugInfoItems: DebugInfo[]) {
44   const settingsHeaders = Object.keys(settings);
45   const companiesHeaders = Object.keys(companies.sort((a, b) => Object.
46     keys(b).length - Object.keys(a).length)[0]);
```

```
43     const debugHeaders = Object.keys(debugInfoItems[0]);
44
45     const settingsData = [settingsHeaders, settingsHeaders.map(h =>
46       settings[h])];
47     const companiesData = [companiesHeaders, ...companies.map(c =>
48       companiesHeaders.map(h => c[h]))];
49     const debugData = [debugHeaders, ...debugInfoItems.map(d =>
50       debugHeaders.map(h => d[h]))];
51
52     const buffer = xlsx.build([
53       { name: 'settings', data: settingsData, options: {} },
54       { name: 'companies', data: companiesData, options: {} },
55       { name: 'debug', data: debugData, options: {} },
56     ]);
57
58     fs.writeFileSync('companies.out.xlsx', buffer, 'binary');
59   }
60
61   interface Settings {
62     productDescription: string;
63     emailSubjectTemplate: string;
64     emailTextTemplate: string;
65     promptWebsiteExtract: string;
66     promptWebsiteChooseContact: string;
67     promptGoogleExtractLink: string;
68     promptGreeting: string;
69   }
70
71   interface CompanyInfo {
72     companyWebsiteUrl: string;
73     companyName: string;
74
75     contactPersonFirstName: string;
76     contactPersonLastName: string;
77     contactPersonEmail: string;
78     contactPersonPosition: string;
79     contactPersonDepartment: string;
80     contactPersonLinkedIn: string;
81
82     personalizedEmailText: string;
83     personalizedEmailSubject: string;
84     personalizedSentence: string;
85   }
86
87   interface DebugInfo {
88     companyWebsiteUrl: string;
89     companyWebsitePageText: string;
```

```
87     companyWebsiteParsedAt: string;
88     hunterIOContactsJSON: string;
89     hunterIOParsedAt: string;
90 }
91
92 const countEmail = (domain: string): Promise<{ total: number }> => {
93     return new Promise((resolve, reject) => {
94         return hunter.emailCount({ domain }, (err, res) => {
95             if (err == null) {
96                 resolve(res.data);
97             } else {
98                 reject(err);
99             }
100         });
101     });
102 };
103
104 const domainSearch = (domain: string) => {
105     return new Promise((resolve, reject) => {
106         return hunter.domainSearch({ domain }, (err, res) => {
107             if (err == null) {
108                 resolve(res.data);
109             } else {
110                 reject(err);
111             }
112         });
113     });
114 };
115
116 async function start() {
117     console.log(': Started');
118
119     const worksheets = xlsx.parse('companies.out.xlsx');
120     const settingsWorksheet: Settings = worksheetDataToObject(worksheets.
121         filter(v => v.name.includes('settings'))[0].data)[0];
122     const companiesWorksheet: CompanyInfo[] = worksheetDataToObject(
123         worksheets.filter(v => v.name.includes('companies'))[0].data);
124     const debugWorksheet: DebugInfo[] = worksheetDataToObject(worksheets.
125         filter(v => v.name.includes('debug'))[0].data);
126
127     const browser = await puppeteer.launch({ headless: true });
128     const page = await browser.newPage();
129     await page.setViewport({ width: 1080, height: 1024 });
130
131     const productDescription: string = settingsWorksheet.
132         productDescription;
133     const emailSubjectTemplate: string = settingsWorksheet.
```

```
    emailSubjectTemplate;
130 const emailTextTemplate: string = settingsWorksheet.emailTextTemplate
    ; // -- I believe that {companyName} will be a great addition to
    our network of sustainability-focused partners and, among other
    things, it can benefit from our ETH students talents pool,
    networking and PR opportunities
131 const promptWebsiteExtract: string = settingsWorksheet.
    promptWebsiteExtract;
132 const promptWebsiteChooseContact: string = settingsWorksheet.
    promptWebsiteChooseContact;
133 const promptGoogleExtractLink: string = settingsWorksheet.
    promptGoogleExtractLink;
134 const promptGreeting: string = settingsWorksheet.promptGreeting;
135
136 let parsedCount: number = 0;
137
138 const debugItems: DebugInfo[] = debugWorksheet;
139
140 for (const c of companiesWorksheet) {
141     if ([
142         c.companyName, c.contactPersonEmail, c.contactPersonFirstName
143         ,
144         c.contactPersonLastName, c.personalizedEmailSubject, c.
            personalizedEmailText,
145         c.personalizedSentence,
146     ].filter(v => v == null).length == 0) {
147         console.log(': Skipping company ${c.companyName}');
148         continue;
149     }
150     console.log(': Visiting company website: ${c.companyWebsiteUrl}')
        ;
151     await page.goto(c.companyWebsiteUrl);
152     await page.waitForTimeout(3_000);
153
154     const companyPageText = await page.$eval('*', (el: any) => el.
        innerText);
155
156     const message = promptWebsiteExtract.replace('{productDescription
        }', productDescription)
        .replace('{emailSubjectTemplate}', emailSubjectTemplate)
157         .replace('{pageText}', companyPageText);
158
159     let promptWebsiteExtractResponse = await gptAPI.sendMessage(
160         message);
161
162     const emailsData = promptWebsiteExtractResponse.text;
```

```
163     console.log('Data: ${emailsData}');
164     const parsedEmailsData = JSON.parse(emailsData);
165
166     const debugItem: DebugInfo = {
167         companyWebsiteUrl: c.companyWebsiteUrl,
168         companyWebsitePageText: companyPageText,
169         companyWebsiteParsedAt: (new Date()).toISOString(),
170         hunterIOContactsJSON: '',
171         hunterIOParsedAt: '',
172     };
173
174     // get contact person from hunter.io based on the website name
175
176     const countEmailsResponse: { total: number } = await countEmail(c
177         .companyWebsiteUrl);
178
179     if (countEmailsResponse.total > 0) {
180         // makes sense to send a query
181         const domainSearchResponse = await domainSearch(c
182             .companyWebsiteUrl);
183
184         const emails = (domainSearchResponse as any).emails;
185
186         const message = replaceAll(promptWebsiteChooseContact, '{
187             emails}', JSON.stringify(emails));
188
189         let promptWebsiteChooseContactResponse = await gptAPI.
190             sendMessage(message, { parentMessageId:
191                 promptWebsiteExtractResponse.id });
192
193         const chosenContactPerson = JSON.parse(
194             promptWebsiteChooseContactResponse.text);
195
196         debugItem.hunterIOContactsJSON = JSON.stringify(
197             domainSearchResponse);
198         debugItem.hunterIOParsedAt = (new Date()).toISOString();
199
200         c.contactPersonFirstName = chosenContactPerson.
201             contactPersonFirstName;
202         c.contactPersonLastName = chosenContactPerson.
203             contactPersonLastName;
204         c.contactPersonEmail = chosenContactPerson.contactPersonEmail
205             ;
206         c.contactPersonPosition = chosenContactPerson.
207             contactPersonPosition;
208         c.contactPersonDepartment = chosenContactPerson.
209             contactPersonDepartment;
```

```
198
199     if (chosenContactPerson.contactPersonLinkedIn == null &&
200         c.contactPersonFirstName != null && c.
201             contactPersonLastName != null) {
202         // get the linkedin page of the person from google
203             search
204
205         const url = 'https://google.com/search?q={firstName}+{
206             lastName}+{companyName}+site%3Alinkedin.com'
207             .replace('{firstName}', c.contactPersonFirstName)
208             .replace('{lastName}', c.contactPersonLastName)
209             .replace('{companyName}', c.companyName);
210
211         const pageView = await browser.newPage();
212         await pageView.goto(url);
213         await pageView.waitForTimeout(3_000);
214         const firstSearchResultElems = await pageView.$x('//html/
215             body/div[7]/div/div[11]/div/div[2]/div[2]/div/div/div
216             [1]');
217         const firstSearchResult = await pageView.evaluate((el:
218             any) => el.innerHTML, firstSearchResultElems[0]);
219
220         const message = promptGoogleExtractLink.replace('{html}',
221             firstSearchResult);
222         let promptGoogleExtractLinkedInLinkResponse = await
223             gptAPI.sendMessage(message);
224         const linkedinProfileLink =
225             promptGoogleExtractLinkedInLinkResponse.text;
226
227         if (linkedinProfileLink != null && linkedinProfileLink.
228             length > 0 && linkedinProfileLink.includes('linkedin.
229             com')) {
230             c.contactPersonLinkedIn = linkedinProfileLink;
231         }
232     } else {
233         c.contactPersonLinkedIn = chosenContactPerson.
234             contactPersonLinkedIn;
235     }
236 }
237
238 // personalize the greeting of the email based on the LinkedIn
239 page content
240
241 let greeting = 'Dear'; // fallback option
242
243 if (c.contactPersonLinkedIn != null) {
244     const page1 = await browser.newPage();
```

```
232     await page1.goto(c.contactPersonLinkedIn);
233     await page1.waitForTimeout(3_000);
234
235     const linkedinProfilePageText = await page1.$eval('*', (el:
        any) => el.innerText);
236
237     const messageGreetingPrompt = promptGreeting.replace('{
        pageContent}', linkedinProfilePageText);
238     let promptGreetingResponse = await gptAPI.sendMessage(
        messageGreetingPrompt);
239     greeting = promptGreetingResponse.text;
240 }
241
242 const personalizedEmailText = replaceAll(
243     replaceAll(
244         replaceAll(
245             replaceAll(emailTextTemplate, '{companyName}',
                parsedEmailsData['companyName']),
246             '{personalizedSentence}',
                parsedEmailsData['personalizedSentence']
247         ),
248         '{contactFirstName}',
249         (c.contactPersonFirstName == null || c.
            contactPersonFirstName == 'null')
250             ? 'Sir/Madam' : c.contactPersonFirstName
251     ), '{greeting}', greeting);
252
253
254 const personalizedEmailSubject = parsedEmailsData['
    personalizedSubject'];
255
256 c.personalizedEmailSubject = personalizedEmailSubject;
257 c.personalizedEmailText = personalizedEmailText;
258 c.personalizedSentence = parsedEmailsData['personalizedSentence
    '];
259 c.companyName = parsedEmailsData['companyName'];
260
261 debugItems.push(debugItem);
262
263 console.log(': Generated for ${c.companyName}');
264
265 parsedCount += 1;
266 }
267
268 console.log(': Parsed count: ${parsedCount}');
269
270 if (parsedCount > 0) {
271     console.log(': Saving parsed data');
```

```

272     saveWorkseets(settingsWorksheet, companiesWorksheet, debugItems);
273   } else {
274     console.log(': No data saved');
275   }
276
277   await browser.close();
278 }
279
280 start();

```

The tool accepts an XLS-file, named 'companies.out.xls', with parameters (prompts and other variables) as an input, and writes the results of its work to the same file.

The XLS-file has 3 sheets with the following structures:

settings:

Column name	Value
productDescription	Description of the sellable product
emailSubjectTemplate	Template for the subject of the email
emailTextTemplate	Template for the text of the email
promptWebsiteExtract	ChatGPT prompt for extracting personalized sentence & company name from a company's website
promptWebsiteChooseContact	ChatGPT prompt for extracting a contact of a person from hunter.io API response
promptGoogleExtractLink	ChatGPT prompt for extracting a contact person's LinkedIn profile from the Google Search results
promptGreeting	ChatGPT prompt for generating a greeting for the personalized email based on the contact person's LinkedIn profile page content

companies:

Column name	Value
companyWebsiteUrl	URL of the company's website; input field
companyName	Name of the company; output field
contactPersonFirstName	First name of the contact person from the company; output field
contactPersonLastName	Last name of the contact person from the company; output field
contactPersonEmail	Personal email of the contact person from the company; output field
personalizedEmailText	Personalized email text for the contact person from the company; output field
personalizedEmailSubject	Personalized email subject for the contact person from the company; output field
personalizedSentence	Personalized sentence to be embedded to the personalized email text of the email; output field
contactPersonPosition	Position of the company's contact person; output field
contactPersonDepartment	Department of the company's contact person; output field
contactPersonLinkedIn	LinkedIn page URL of the company's contact person; output field

debug:

Column name	Value
companyWebsiteUrl	URL of the company's website
companyWebsitePageText	Scraped text of the company's web page
companyWebsiteParsedAt	Date when the company website was parsed
hunterIOContactsJSON	hunter.io API response JSON content
hunterIOParsedAt	Date when the hunter.io's API response was retrieved and parsed

Chapter 5

Results

5.1 Key findings and contributions of the study results

The research defined and implemented an approach to improve the efficiency of the outbound marketing phase in the context of B2B sales. The validation of the approach defined in this thesis in the context of a ETH EC project indicates that Large Language Model (LLM)-based technologies for optimizing B2B sales processes largely improve productivity.

Upon implementing the tool, a significant transformation occurred in the approach to outbound marketing. Previously, the process involved time-consuming and sequential manual research for each company and its corresponding contact person, demanding approximately 5 minutes per company for the individuals involved in the research activities. However, with the introduction of automated functionalities provided by the tool, most email personalization tasks became delegable. Consequently, the work process transitioned into a sequential series of steps, including configuring the tool for a specific project (performed on a per-product basis), inputting website addresses, and scheduling the delivery of generated email messages. The initial step of the outbound marketing process underwent complete automation and delegation to the ChatGPT+puppeteer+hunter.io+linkedin based tool, which was developed throughout the research and development process. Remarkably, the tool successfully optimized the process of generating personalized emails, leading to a significant reduction in the time required to approximately 30 seconds per company. The implementation of the tool facilitated enhanced scalability of the initial step of the outbound marketing process, shifting the bottleneck from the company research activity to the collection of company websites.

5.2 Findings on limitations of ChatGPT in scope of the study

The study primarily focused on investigating two use cases for LLM-based technologies in the automation of outbound marketing:

1. Extracting valuable information from unstructured data: ChatGPT effectively tackled this task by analyzing scraped web pages and identifying relevant details such as company names, email addresses, names of individuals, positions, and departments. The generated information was structured and in a format suitable for subsequent machine processing

(JSON). The prompts used for ChatGPT in data extraction were concise and straightforward to manage.

2. Generating personalized texts: LLM-based technologies, specifically ChatGPT, demonstrated proficiency in generating personalized text content. It effectively crafted tailored messages based on the given inputs, allowing for enhanced customization in outbound marketing communications.

Overall, the study highlights the successful utilization of LLM-based technologies, specifically ChatGPT, in addressing the challenges of data extraction and generating personalized texts in the context of outbound marketing automation. The prompts used for data extraction were concise and easy to maintain, enabling efficient processing of unstructured information.

During the research and development process, the author faced the following limitations of ChatGPT:

1. Non-deterministic nature of the model and high variety of possible generated outputs for same prompts: when experimenting with generation of personalized email texts with the use of ChatGPT, the author was facing situations when the same prompt would yield different outcomes, and not all of them were equally suitable for the intended purposes. To mitigate this behavior the author narrowed down the amount of generated personalized text to one sentence. Embedding this one sentence into a pre-defined template of an email message was enough to guarantee a predictable level of quality for the generated personalization, which, according to Julien Boudet, Brian Gregg, Kathryn Rathje, Eli Stein, and Kai Vollhardt will be the prime driver of marketing success within five years[22].
2. Limited context window: ChatGPT has a limited amount of tokens it can consider when generating a response. In scope of this research the author rarely faced situations when the amount of text that required processing was exceeding the limitation. However, this context window limitation problem can be of a high significance in tasks that require processing of bigger amounts of input data, which leads to the challenge of horizontal scaling of the model.

5.3 Potential areas for future research

The author recommends the following area as a potential avenue for future research on LLMs:

1. Horizontal scaling of the model context window size: although context window size of LLMs will be constantly increasing, there will always be tasks that require an even bigger context window than current LLMs can offer (e.g. tasks, requiring from models processing of high volumes of real-time data). Horizontal scaling, according to CloudZero team[33], is a term from infrastructure management that suggests approaching the problem of scaling limited VM resources by adding more computational nodes and distributing the growing workload across these added computational nodes (versus increasing computational resources of a single physical machine).
2. Security (prompt injections): LLMs are getting integrated to new products more and more often these days. In many cases, if not thought through, such integrations can pose

various security risks, related to prompt injections. A prompt injection, like well-known SQL-injection as described by w3schools[9], is an attack when there is a user input that is supposed to be processed by an LLM, and that input contains malicious instructions for the LLM. Such malicious input can lead to exposure of data or re-instruction of the model.

3. Efficient communication of LLMs with other AI models: the deeper the penetration of LLMs into our society, the more often LLMs will be tasked with processing data, generated by other LLMs. In some cases we can even talk of AI models chaining (e.g. using LLMs to generate prompts for models of other modalities, such as DALL-E). Efficient communication of LLMs can result in significant reduction of costs associated with the maintenance of AI models.

5.4 Recommendations for sales teams on how to leverage the tool to optimize their B2B sales process

The tool developed as part of this master's thesis research and development process significantly improves the efficiency of the initial stage of outbound marketing in B2B sales. By leveraging LLM (ChatGPT in particular) for automating the labor-intensive and time-consuming tasks involved in researching potential partners, the tool streamlines the process and yields notable efficiency gains.

The tool offers substantial advantages to sales teams, with the efficiency benefits being amplified by the team's size. To optimize the tool's effectiveness, the author proposes reorganizing the responsibilities within the sales or marketing team according to the following pipeline:

1. The lead salesperson in the sales team takes on the responsibility of manually defining several crucial aspects:
 - (a) The comprehensive description of the product that will be marketed and sold.
 - (b) The template for the selling email, outlining the general structure of the initial communication step.
 - (c) The subject line of the selling email, which aims to capture the recipient's attention.
 - (d) The detailed profile of the ideal target customer, encompassing specific characteristics and preferences.
2. Subsequently, the other members of the sales team utilize the meticulously defined target customer profile to conduct a thorough search for relevant companies. Their objective is to identify websites of companies that potentially align with the established target customer profile. The collected website URLs are then organized and stored in an Excel file for further usage.
3. At this stage, a responsible member of the sales team assumes the responsibility of reviewing the compiled Excel file containing all the gathered website URLs. Their role is to carefully assess the collected information for accuracy and completeness. Once the review is complete, they proceed to launch the personalized outbound marketing campaign, leveraging the compiled data to tailor the communication to the specific target companies and individuals.

By following these systematic steps, sales teams can optimize their outbound marketing campaigns, aiming to achieve the highest possible throughput and effectiveness in reaching and engaging their target audience.

Bibliography

- [1] Chatgpt. URL: <https://chat.openai.com>.
- [2] Eth entrepreneur club. URL: <https://www.entrepreneur-club.org>.
- [3] Find out how to connect gpt-3 to your sendpulse chatbot. URL: <https://sendpulse.com/support/glossary/chatgpt>.
- [4] How to use smart personalization in emails. URL: <https://sendpulse.com/knowledge-base/email-service/additional/clever-personalization>.
- [5] hunter.io. URL: <https://hunter.io>.
- [6] Linkedin. URL: <https://linkedin.com/>.
- [7] Mailing list segmentation. URL: <https://sendpulse.com/features/email-segmentation>.
- [8] Salesforce announces einstein gpt, the world's first generative ai for crm. URL: <https://www.salesforce.com/news/press-releases/2023/03/07/einstein-generative-ai/>.
- [9] Sql injection. URL: https://www.w3schools.com/sql/sql_injection.asp.
- [10] Trigger marketing. URL: <https://sendpulse.com/support/glossary/trigger-marketing>.
- [11] A.S.Gabrio Martin A. Shaji George¹, A.S. Hovan George². A review of chatgpt ai's impact on several business sectors. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7644359>, February 15, 2023.
- [12] Marvellous Aham-adi. 8 strategies to help you increase email response rates. URL: <https://www.sendx.io/blog/email-response-rates>, 2023.
- [13] Katelyn Bourgoin. The ultimate guide to buying triggers: How marketers can use trigger events to reduce costs and drive sales. URL: <https://customercamp.co/ultimate-guide-buying-triggers/>.
- [14] Devin Coldewey. 5 ways gpt-4 outsmarts chatgpt. URL: <https://techcrunch.com/2023/03/14/5-ways-gpt-4-outsmarts-chatgpt>, March 2023.
- [15] Ray Collis. *Quick Win B2B Sales*. Oak Tree Press; First Edition, 2010.

- [16] Botpress Community. List of languages supported by chatgpt. URL: <https://botpress.com/blog/list-of-languages-supported-by-chatgpt>, April 2023.
- [17] GitHub community. Chatgpt awesome list. URL: <https://github.com/eon01/awesome-chatgpt>, 2023.
- [18] Sam Crowder. Large language models will redefine b2b software. URL: <https://baincapitalventures.com/insight/large-language-models-will-redefine-b2b-software/>, October 2022.
- [19] Antoine Fink. How to do cold emailing after the gdpr. URL: <https://hunter.io/blog/how-to-do-cold-emailing-after-the-gdpr/>, June 2018.
- [20] Cezary Gesikowski. Chatgpt vs grammarly: Who wins the battle of grammatical error correction? URL: <https://bootcamp.uxdesign.cc/chatgpt-vs-grammarly-who-wins-the-battle-of-grammatical-error-correction-b988b9c20e5b>, March 2023.
- [21] Lena Hohenschwert. *Making B2B Sales Interactions Valuable - A Social and Symbolic Perspective*. Institute of Economic Research, 2012.
- [22] Kathryn Rathje Eli Stein Kai Vollhardt Julien Boudet, Brian Gregg. The future of personalization and how to get ready for it. URL: <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/growth-marketing-and-sales/our-insights/the-future-of-personalization-and-how-to-get-ready-for-it>, June 2019.
- [23] kangalow. Chatgpt – 4 useful insights. URL: <https://jetsonhacks.com/2023/04/24/chatgpt-4-useful-insights/>, April 2023.
- [24] Sahil Kapoor. What is the chatgpt token limit and can you exceed it? URL: <https://www.makeuseof.com/what-is-chatgpt-token-limit-can-you-exceed-it/>, May 2023.
- [25] Swati Aggarwal Kavita Sharma. *Digital Marketing Outreach: The Future of Marketing Practices*. London, 2022.
- [26] Yasin Küçükaya. 7 major differences between the new fadp and gdpr. URL: <https://www.adnovum.com/blog/swiss-data-protection-law-how-the-new-fadp-differs-from-the-gdpr>, February 2023.
- [27] Kerry Leech. Building credibility: The key to winning b2b clients. URL: <https://www.rooandeve.com/blog/building-credibility-the-key-to-winning-b2b-clients>.
- [28] Jason Cherek Kelsey Robinson Marc Brodherson, Adam Broitman. A customer-centric approach to marketing in a privacy-first world. URL: <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/growth-marketing-and-sales/our-insights/a-customer-centric-approach-to-marketing-in-a-privacy-first-world>, May 2021.
- [29] Bernard Marr. The top 10 limitations of chatgpt. URL: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/bernardmarr/2023/03/03/the-top-10-limitations-of-chatgpt/>, March 2023.

- [30] Julia McCoy. What is the average response rate of cold emails in 2023? URL: <https://contentatscale.ai/average-response-rate-of-cold-emails/>, 2023.
- [31] Anand Shah. 3 ways to scale strategic b2b selling. URL: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesbusinessdevelopmentcouncil/2023/04/12/3-ways-to-scale-strategic-b2b-selling/>, April 2023.
- [32] Joseph Sugarman. *Triggers: 30 Sales Tools you can use to Control the Mind of your Prospect to Motivate, Influence and Persuade*. Delstar Pub, 1999.
- [33] CloudZero Team. Horizontal vs. vertical scaling: How do they compare? URL: <https://www.cloudzero.com/blog/horizontal-vs-vertical-scaling>, May 2023.
- [34] GL CONTENT TEAM. Lead follow-up best practices for b2b leads. URL: <https://goodmanlantern.com/blog/lead-follow-up-best-practices-for-b2b-leads/>, March 2023.
- [35] MailChimp Content Marketing team. Email marketing statistics and benchmarks by industry. URL: <https://mailchimp.com/resources/email-marketing-benchmarks/>.
- [36] StreetDigital team. What is salesforce einstein gpt? URL: <https://6st.co/what-is-salesforce-einstein-gpt/>, March 2023.
- [37] Anthony W. Ulwick. *Jobs to be Done: Theory to Practice*. IDEA BITE PRESS, January 2016.
- [38] Riya Uppal. A complete guide to b2b data compliance and cold outreach. URL: <https://hubsell.com/insights/b2b-data-compliance/>, May 2022.
- [39] Indian Institute of Management Parvathy Parvathy Emmanuel Mogaji Varsha Jain, Himanshu Rai. The prospects and challenges of chatgpt on marketing research and practices. URL: <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4398033>, April 2023.
- [40] Phil Wainwright. Drilling into einstein gpt - is generative ai trustworthy enough for enterprise use cases? URL: <https://diginomica.com/einstein-gpt-generative-ai-trustworthy-enterprise-use>, March 2023.
- [41] Jonathan L. York and Jeffrey E. Danes. Customer development, innovation, and decision-making biases in the lean startup. *Journal of Small Business Strategy (archive only)*, 24(2):21–40, May 2014.